

Subject-Independent Thermal Infrared Intoxication Detection: Periorbital Deep Learning with Explainability Analysis

Arghya Dev Mondal^{a,*} Harkeerat Kaur^a

^aDepartment of Computer Science and Engineering
Indian Institute of Technology Jammu, Jammu 181221, India

*Corresponding author: 2023pai9234@iitjammu.ac.in

Abstract

Breathalyser based alcohol screening in aviation covers only a fraction of safety-sensitive personnel on any given day, leaving a substantial gap in workforce monitoring. Thermal infrared imaging could help fill this gap, since alcohol consumption raises skin temperature through peripheral vasodilation, and these changes can be picked up passively without any contact. In this work, we apply deep learning to thermal facial images from the University of Patras Sober-Drunk dataset and evaluate performance using Leave-One-Subject-Out Cross-Validation (LOSO-CV), which ensures that the model is always tested on individuals it has never seen during training. Prior studies in this area used subject-dependent evaluation and reported accuracies of 86–98%, but such protocols are known to overestimate performance. Under our subject-independent protocol, the periorbital region proved to be the most informative imaging site (MCC = 0.537, accuracy = 76.2%), and Grad-CAM visualisations confirmed that the model focuses on the periorbital vasculature, which is consistent with where alcohol-induced vasodilation is physiologically expected. We also found that Gaussian noise augmentation, commonly used in image classification, caused the model to lose its focus on thermal gradients altogether, a form of feature collapse verified through Grad-CAM. Fusing periorbital and facial predictions improved both discrimination (MCC = 0.565) and probability calibration (ECE = 0.156). However, around 30% of subjects remained difficult to classify regardless of the model or hyperparameters used, pointing to underlying physiological variability that no amount of architectural tuning could resolve. We propose a practical deployment model where thermal screening acts as a first-pass filter, and anyone flagged is sent for a confirmatory breathalyser test.

Keywords: Thermal infrared imaging; Alcohol intoxication; Deep learning; Subject-independent evaluation; Leave-one-subject-out cross-validation; Periorbital region; Grad-CAM; Probability calibration; Aviation safety screening; Responsible AI

1 Introduction

Alcohol intoxication among personnel in safety-critical industries presents a well-documented risk to operational safety. In aviation, even moderate intoxication degrades cognitive function, reaction time, and motor coordination [1]. Regulatory bodies worldwide enforce strict controls. The International Civil Aviation Organisation (ICAO) prohibits licence holders from operating under the influence of any psychoactive substances [1], the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) of USA, enforces 14 CFR § 91.17 [2], the European Union Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) mandates systematic random testing under Commission Regulation (EU) 2018/1042 [3], and the Directorate General of Civil Aviation (DGCA) of India requires mandatory pre-flight breathalyser testing for flight and ground crew [4, 5].

Despite these regulatory requirements, implementation faces practical resource constraints. Breathalyser testing requires trained medical personnel, dedicated equipments and consumable resources. While flight-crew typically undergo comprehensive screening, ground handling personnel, maintenance

engineers, and air traffic controllers are subject to random sampling at rates as low as 25% per day [5], leaving the majority of safety-sensitive ground personnel untested on any given day. This coverage gap represents a systemic vulnerability.

Thermal infrared imaging offers potential complement to existing screening methods. Alcohol consumption induces peripheral vasodilation, increasing cutaneous blood flow and elevating skin surface temperature [6, 7]. These physiological changes are detectable through thermal imaging which is passive, contactless and amenable to high-throughput deployment. Modern uncooled microbolometer cameras with thermal sensitivity below 50 mK are increasingly available at accessible price points [8], making practical deployment more feasible.

Prior research has explored thermal based intoxication detection using both handcrafted features [7, 9, 36] and deep learning [10–12, 43, 45], with reported accuracies ranging from 77% to 98%. However, a careful examination of the literature reveals several methodological gaps that limit confidence in these findings. Most studies employed subject-dependent evaluation protocols which permits the same individual to appear in both training and testing partitions, a practice known to inflate

accuracy by 20–30 percentage points in comparable physiological classification tasks [13, 37]. Systematic comparison of anatomical imaging sites, interpretability analysis, and alignment with emerging regulatory frameworks for high-risk AI applications [15, 16] remain largely unaddressed. Section 2 reviews these prior works in detail and identifies the specific gaps that motivate the present study.

To address these gaps, the present work conducts a six-stage empirical investigation with the following contributions:

- (i) Subject-independent LOSO-CV benchmarks for thermal intoxication detection using a public dataset with a larger cohort ($N = 34$) than prior subject-independent work ($N = 10$) [12], providing calibrated performance expectations for system design.
- (ii) Systematic comparison of four anatomical regions (face, periorbital, auricular, palmar) under identical experimental conditions, offering evidence based guidance for imaging site selection.
- (iii) Comprehensive sensitivity analysis of learning rates, temporal sampling density, regularisation strategies, and backbone architectures (ResNet-18, EfficientNet-B0, MobileNet-V2, DenseNet-121) including the finding that standard augmentation techniques can induce feature collapse in thermal imagery.
- (iv) Grad-CAM explainability analysis validating physiological plausibility of learned features and revealing failure modes, addressing EASA AI Explainability requirements [15].
- (v) Score-level fusion of complementary modalities with probability calibration assessment, yielding two deployment-ready operating strategies for different cost structures.
- (vi) Characterisation of a ‘Non-Responder Phenomenon’ wherein approximately 30% of subjects remain challenging regardless of model configuration, with implications for algorithmic fairness and the practical limits of thermal-based screening.

The remainder of this paper is organised as follows: Section 2 reviews prior work and identifies research gaps. Section 3 describes the dataset, preprocessing, model architectures, and experimental design. Section 4 presents experimental results across all six stages. Section 5 discusses findings in relation to prior work, physiological interpretation and deployment considerations. Section 6 summarises contributions and outlines directions for future research.

2 Related Work

2.1 Thermal Imaging for Intoxication Detection

The use of thermal infrared imaging for intoxication detection was established by Koukiou and Anastassopoulos in a series of studies using the University of Patras dataset. Their initial work [36] extracted statistical features (temperature histograms, spatial moments) from facial thermal images and

applied clustering-based classification, reporting 86% identification accuracy on 20 subjects. A subsequent study [7] applied neural network classifiers to facial thermal imagery, identifying the forehead region as the most discriminative area and achieving comparable discrimination on 41 subjects. Their periorbital-focused work [9] analysed sclera temperature distributions using histogram-based methods, correctly identifying 36 of 41 intoxicated subjects (approximately 88%).

Beyond this foundational work, Hermosilla et al. [47] applied Weber Local Descriptors and Local Binary Patterns to the PUCV-DTF dataset (46 subjects), achieving 87% accuracy using a Gaussian mixture model classifier, demonstrating feasibility across independent datasets. Sancén-Plaza et al. [43] applied handcrafted features on the PUCV-DTF dataset, Bhuyan et al. [44] explored multimodal analysis combining thermal signatures with gait, and Chai et al. [45] applied CNNs and YOLO to the Tufts Face Database. However, these studies either used different datasets, combined non-thermal modalities, or did not report classification metrics directly comparable to the present work.

2.2 Deep Learning Approaches

More recent work has applied deep convolutional neural networks (CNNs) to this task. Neagoe and Carata [10] used a neural network-based approach on facial thermal images from the E-Health Bioengineering Conference, achieving moderate accuracy. Soltuz and Neagoe [11] explicitly employed subject-dependent protocols with multiple CNN architectures, achieving 93–98% accuracy and establishing an upper bound for known-identity scenarios. Neagoe and Diaconescu [12] proposed an ensemble of deep CNNs evaluated under a subject-independent protocol on a subset of 10 subjects, achieving 95.75% accuracy; however, the small sample limits the statistical validity and generalisability of these findings. Recently, Chai et al. [45] applied CNNs and YOLO-based architectures to thermal facial images from the Tufts Face Database, achieving 90% accuracy with subject-dependent evaluation.

2.3 Evaluation Methodology Concerns

A critical issue across this literature is the evaluation protocol. Most studies employed conventional train-test splits or k -fold cross-validation that permitted samples from the same individual to appear in both training and testing partitions. This subject-dependent evaluation allows models to exploit subject-specific thermal patterns rather than learning intoxication-specific features. The consequence of this methodological choice is well documented in adjacent domains: Kunjan et al. [13] demonstrated that subject-dependent protocols inflated EEG classification accuracy by 20–30 percentage points compared to LOSO-CV, and Lotte [37] noted the evolution toward subject-independent evaluation as a methodological standard in brain-computer interface research. Mansfield and Wayman [14] established similar requirements for biometric system evaluation.

Table 1: Summary of prior work on thermal-based intoxication detection using dedicated datasets. SD: subject-dependent; SI: subject-independent.

Study	Year	N	Method	Protocol	Acc (%)
Koukiou [36]	2012	20	Clustering	SD	86
Koukiou [7]	2015	41	NN	SD	~88
Koukiou [9]	2016	41	Histogram	SD	~88
Neagoe [12]	2020	10	CNN Ensemble	SI	95.8
Soltuz [11]	2021	41	CNN	SD	93–98
Koukiou [46]	2022	41	SVM	SD	>86
Chai [45]	2025	20	MLP	SD	90

Table 1 summarises the prior work, evaluation protocols, and reported performance. The only prior subject-independent deep learning evaluation [12] used a private subset of just 10 subjects, limiting generalisability.

2.4 Explainability and Responsible AI

Interpretability of model decisions has received limited attention in thermal intoxication detection. No prior study in this domain has applied gradient-based visualisation methods such as Grad-CAM [33] to validate that learned features correspond to physiologically relevant regions. This gap is notable given the increasing regulatory emphasis on explainability for high-risk AI systems. The EASA Concept Paper [15] distinguishes between development explainability (for engineers) and operational explainability (for end users), while the EU AI Act [16] (Article 13) mandates transparency requirements for high-risk applications. Probability calibration [27] and fairness assessment, both relevant to trustworthy deployment, have similarly not been addressed in prior thermal intoxication studies.

2.5 Summary of Research Gaps

The reviewed literature establishes the physiological basis and feasibility of thermal intoxication detection, while revealing the following gaps that motivate the present study: (a) the absence of subject-independent evaluation using LOSO-CV on a sufficiently large public dataset; (b) no systematic comparison of anatomical imaging sites under controlled conditions; (c) no interpretability analysis validating physiological plausibility of learned features; (d) no assessment of probability calibration or algorithmic fairness; and (e) no explicit alignment with emerging aviation AI regulatory frameworks.

3 Materials and Methods

3.1 Dataset

This study utilises the University of Patras Sober-Drunk Dataset [7, 9], a publicly available thermal infrared dataset comprising thermal sequences from 41 participants. Thermal

images were acquired using a FLIR ThermoVision Micron (A10) infrared camera (128×160 pixels, 14-bit data stored in 16-bit TIFF, LWIR $7.5\text{--}13.5 \mu\text{m}$). During initial data auditing, seven participants (Subjects 9, 11, 12, 13, 14, 20 & 24) were excluded due to missing thermal sequences or corrupted TIFF files which prevented consistent extraction across all four modalities and time points, ensuring strict data integrity. This yielded an experimental group of 34 subjects (25 males, 9 female).

Each participant consumed 480 mL of red wine (13% ABV) over an hour. Thermal sequences were captured at four time points, sober baseline, 20 minutes post-consumption, 50 minutes post-consumption, and 80 minutes post-consumption. At each time point, four anatomical modalities were recorded, face (frontal view), periorbital (periocular region), ear (lateral view), and hand (palmar). Each recording comprised of 50 sequential frames captured at 100 ms intervals. For present binary classification study, only sober (Sequence 1) and intoxicated (Sequence 4, 80 minutes post-consumption) images were utilised. The 80-minute post-consumption sequences were deliberately selected as it aligns with the established pharmacokinetic window for peak Blood Alcohol Concentration (BAC) [17] and maximum alcohol-induced peripheral vasodilation following acute consumption. Evaluating the maximum physiological response aligns with binary pass/fail requirements of regulatory screening. It establishes a bounding baseline for system efficacy before future work investigates intermediate metabolic phases.

3.2 Data Preprocessing

Thermal images were normalised using fold-specific (training-set specific) min-max scaling to the $[0, 1]$ range, preventing information leakage from the test subjects. Given an image $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times W}$ and training-set statistics $X_{\min}^{(\text{train})}$ and $X_{\max}^{(\text{train})}$, the normalised image is:

$$\hat{\mathbf{X}} = \frac{\mathbf{X} - X_{\min}^{(\text{train})}}{X_{\max}^{(\text{train})} - X_{\min}^{(\text{train})}} \quad (1)$$

Single channel thermal images were replicated across three channels to match the input requirements of ImageNet-pretrained models. Spatial preprocessing included resizing to 224×224 pixels (bilinear interpolation). Online data augmentation during training comprised random horizontal flipping ($p = 0.5$), random rotation ($\pm 10^\circ$), and random affine translation ($\pm 5\%$ spatial extent).

3.3 Model Architecture and Transfer Learning

The baseline architecture for this study employed ResNet-18 [18] pre-trained on ImageNet [19]. The final classification layer was replaced with a custom head comprising dropout ($p = 0.5$) and a single linear unit mapped to a sigmoid output, applied on top of the architecture’s built-in global average

pooling:

$$\hat{y} = \sigma(\mathbf{w}^\top \cdot \text{GAP}(f_\theta(\hat{\mathbf{X}})) + b) \quad (2)$$

where $f_\theta(\cdot)$ denotes the convolutional feature extractor, $\text{GAP}(\cdot)$ is global average pooling, $\sigma(\cdot)$ is the sigmoid function, and $\hat{y} \in [0, 1]$ represents the predicted probability of intoxication. During fine-tuning, all network layers were updated. Three alternative architectures were additionally evaluated in Stage 5: EfficientNet-B0 (5.3M parameters) [20], MobileNet-V2 (3.5M parameters) [21], and DenseNet-121 (8.0M parameters) [22].

3.4 Experimental Design

The investigation was structured as a six-stage exploratory ablation study (Table 4). This was designed as a sensitivity analysis rather than a formal hyperparameter optimization pipeline. The objective of Stages 2-5 was not to tune a final deployable model which would risk data leakage if test folds implicitly informed hyperparameter selection, but rather to systematically evaluate the sensitivity of thermal feature extraction to isolated variations. Stage 1 compared four anatomical modalities using a baseline configuration. Stages 2-5 systematically varied a single variable: learning rate (Stage 2), temporal frame sampling density (Stage 3), regularisation and augmentation strategies (Stage 4), and backbone architecture (Stage 5). Stage 6 investigated score-level fusion of the two highest-MCC modalities (periorbital and facial) from Stage 1.

3.5 Leave-One-Subject-Out Cross-Validation

All experiments employed Leave-One-Subject-Out Cross-Validation (LOSO-CV) across $N = 34$ subjects. In each fold k , all images from subject k comprised the test set $\mathcal{D}_k^{\text{test}}$ while images from the remaining 33 subjects formed the training set $\mathcal{D}_k^{\text{train}}$:

$$\mathcal{D}_k^{\text{train}} = \bigcup_{j \neq k} \mathcal{D}_j, \quad \mathcal{D}_k^{\text{test}} = \mathcal{D}_k, \quad k = 1, \dots, N \quad (3)$$

This protocol ensures complete independence between training and testing partitions, preventing information leakage through subject-specific features [13, 14]. Five frames were randomly sampled (with fixed seed) from each 50-frame sequence at dataset loading, yielding approximately 330 training images per fold (33 subjects \times 2 sequences \times 5 frames).

3.6 Training Procedure

Models were optimised using the Adam optimiser [23] with learning rate $\eta = 1 \times 10^{-5}$, $\beta_1 = 0.9$, $\beta_2 = 0.999$, and binary cross-entropy loss with logits (numerically equivalent to applying sigmoid then BCE):

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{BCE}} = -\frac{1}{M} \sum_{i=1}^M [y_i \log(\hat{y}_i) + (1 - y_i) \log(1 - \hat{y}_i)] \quad (4)$$

where $y_i \in \{0, 1\}$ is the ground truth and \hat{y}_i is the predicted probability for sample i in a mini-batch of size M . Training proceeded for a maximum of 100 epochs with early stopping (patience = 20 epochs) based on validation loss, where 10% of training images were randomly held out as a validation subset for early stopping and learning rate scheduling. Experiments were conducted on NVIDIA Tesla P100 GPU (16 GB) using PyTorch 2.1. Random seeds were fixed at 42 for reproducibility. All 578 training runs (17 configurations \times 34 folds) were logged via Weights & Biases.

3.7 Score-Level Fusion

Stage 6 investigated score level fusion at two levels. First, intra-modal frame aggregation (6A) computed the mean predicted probability across the five frames per subject-condition pair to produce a single subject-level score; this step also served as the prerequisite for inter-modal fusion:

$$\bar{P}_m = \frac{1}{5} \sum_{t=1}^5 \hat{y}_{m,t} \quad (5)$$

where $m \in \{\text{eye}, \text{face}\}$ and t indexes the temporal frames.

Second, inter-modal fusion via the Minimum Probability Rule (6B) [24] combined periorbital or eye region and facial predictions:

$$\hat{P}_{\min} = \min(\bar{P}_{\text{eye}}, \bar{P}_{\text{face}}) \quad (6)$$

where \bar{P}_{eye} and \bar{P}_{face} are the subject-level aggregated probabilities. This conservative strategy classifies a subject as intoxicated only when both eye and face modalities agree, effectively implementing a logical AND operation which prioritises specificity. Third, Maximum Probability Rule (6C) applied the complementary operation:

$$\hat{P}_{\max} = \max(\bar{P}_{\text{eye}}, \bar{P}_{\text{face}}) \quad (7)$$

This strategy classifies a subject as intoxicated when either of these two modality indicates intoxication, implementing a logical OR operation prioritising sensitivity at the cost of specificity.

3.8 Evaluation Metrics

The **Matthews Correlation Coefficient** (MCC) [25, 26] served as the primary evaluation metric for its robustness to class imbalance and consideration of all four quadrants of the confusion matrix:

$$\text{MCC} = \frac{TP \cdot TN - FP \cdot FN}{\sqrt{(TP + FP)(TP + FN)(TN + FP)(TN + FN)}} \quad (8)$$

where TP , TN , FP , FN denote true positives, true negatives, false positives, and false negatives. MCC ranges from -1 (total disagreement) through 0 (random) to $+1$ (perfect), and is robust to class imbalance. Secondary metrics also included accuracy, sensitivity (recall), specificity, ROC-AUC, Equal Error Rate (EER), and Expected Calibration Error (ECE) [27].

The **Equal Error Rate** (EER) is the operating point where false acceptance rate equals false rejection rate:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{EER} &= \text{FAR}(\tau^*) = \text{FRR}(\tau^*), \\ \tau^* &= \arg \min_{\tau} |\text{FAR}(\tau) - \text{FRR}(\tau)| \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

The **Expected Calibration Error** (ECE) [27] quantifies the alignment between predicted probabilities and observed frequencies:

$$\text{ECE} = \sum_{b=1}^B \frac{n_b}{N} |\text{acc}(b) - \text{conf}(b)| \quad (10)$$

where samples are partitioned into B equal-width bins, n_b is the number of samples in bin b , $\text{acc}(b)$ is the observed accuracy, and $\text{conf}(b)$ is the mean predicted confidence in bin b . $B = 5$ equal-width bins were used for all ECE calculations in this study, this departs from the 15-bin convention of Guo et al. [27] but is appropriate given the small sample sizes involved (as few as 68 observations at the subject level in Stage 6), which would leave many bins sparsely populated under the standard 15-bin scheme.

Statistical comparisons followed the recommendations of Demšar [28] for comparing multiple classifiers, the Friedman test [29] as omnibus test, Wilcoxon signed-rank tests [30] for pairwise comparisons, and Holm-Bonferroni correction [31] used for multiple comparisons. Effect sizes were reported as Cohen’s d [32].

3.9 Explainability Analysis

Gradient-weighted Class Activation Mapping (Grad-CAM) [33] was applied to the final convolutional layer of each architecture to visualise the discriminative regions. For a target class c and feature maps A^k at the final convolutional layer, Grad-CAM computes:

$$\alpha_k^c = \frac{1}{Z} \sum_i \sum_j \frac{\partial y^c}{\partial A_{ij}^k} \quad (11)$$

$$L_{\text{Grad-CAM}}^c = \text{ReLU} \left(\sum_k \alpha_k^c A^k \right) \quad (12)$$

where α_k^c represents the importance weight of feature map k for class c , computed by global average-pooling the gradients of the target class score with respect to each of the feature map, $Z = H \times W$ is the spatial dimensionality and the ReLU ensures only features with positive influence are highlighted, producing a class discriminative localisation heatmap. This analysis addresses EASA’s AI Explainability requirements [15] which distinguish between development explainability and operational explainability.

Table 2: Classification performance across all four anatomical modalities (Stage 1). Values represent mean \pm standard deviation across 34 LOSO-CV folds. Bold indicates best performance.

ID	Modality	MCC	Acc	Sens	Spec	AUC	EER↓	ECE↓
1A	Face	.407±.578	70.0	75.9	64.1	.815	.171	.295
1B	Eye	.537±.463	76.2	79.4	72.9	.869	.118	.260
1C	Ear	.347±.549	67.1	68.8	65.3	.806	.191	.298
1D	Hand	.391±.623	68.8	69.4	68.2	.738	.271	.302

Table 3: Pairwise statistical comparisons of MCC scores across all four modalities (Stage 1). $n = 34$ subjects per fold. Effect size magnitudes: $|d| < 0.2$ negligible, $0.2 \leq |d| < 0.5$ small, $0.5 \leq |d| < 0.8$ medium, $|d| \geq 0.8$ large.

Comparison	ΔMean	W	p_{corr}	d	Effect
Face vs. Eye	−0.131	72.5	1.000	−0.250	Small
Face vs. Ear	0.060	89.0	1.000	0.106	Negl.
Face vs. Hand	0.015	72.0	1.000	0.025	Negl.
Eye vs. Ear	0.190	64.5	0.802	0.375	Small
Eye vs. Hand	0.146	108.0	1.000	0.266	Small
Ear vs. Hand	−0.044	129.5	1.000	−0.076	Negl.

4 Results

4.1 Stage 1: Modality Comparison

Table 2 presents the classification performance across all four anatomical modalities. The periorbital (eye) region demonstrated superior performance across all evaluation criteria, achieving the highest MCC (0.537 ± 0.463), accuracy (76.2%), sensitivity (79.4%), and specificity (72.9%). The high standard deviation 0.463 reflects the substantial inter-subject variability, with individual fold MCC values ranging from 0.000 to 1.000 indicating that the model achieved perfect classification for some subjects while performing at chance level for others. Discriminative capacity, as measured by ROC-AUC further corroborated periorbital superiority (0.869 ± 0.286), with the lowest standard deviation indicating most consistent discrimination across subjects. The periorbital (eye) modality also achieved the lowest EER (0.118) and best probability calibration (ECE=0.260).

The Friedman test revealed no statistically significant omnibus differences in MCC across modalities ($\chi^2(3) = 1.52$, $p = 0.678$), attributable to high inter-subject variability and modest sample size. However, pairwise comparisons (Table 3) revealed consistent small effect sizes favouring the periorbital region over the auricular/ear ($d = 0.375$) and palmar/hand ($d = 0.266$) modalities.

Grad-CAM analysis provided the mechanistic insight into modality differences (Fig. 1). The periorbital (eye) model learned class-specific attention patterns, compact, lateralised periorbital focus for sober samples versus broad bilateral expansion encompassing the nasal bridge and infraorbital zones for intoxicated samples. This differentiation is consistent with alcohol-induced vasodilation affecting the periorbital and nasal

Figure 1: Grad-CAM visualisations for periorbital (eye) modality (Stage 1). Top row: sober samples showing compact, lateralised periorbital attention. Bottom row: intoxicated samples with broad bilateral activation encompassing the nasal bridge and infraorbital regions consistent with alcohol-induced vasodilation.

vasculature [6, 34]. The facial model exhibited broader, less specific activation, while the palmar model showed inconsistent attention without clear anatomical correspondence.

4.2 Stages 2-5: Configuration Optimisation

Table 4 presents comprehensive performance across all configurations evaluated in Stages 2-5. The baseline configuration (1B: ResNet-18, LR = 1×10^{-5} , 5 frames, Adam, no augmentation) maintained highest overall MCC (0.537) and lowest EER (0.118).

4.2.1 Learning Rate (Stage 2)

Learning rates of 5×10^{-6} , 2×10^{-5} , and 5×10^{-5} were compared against the baseline (1×10^{-5}). Progressive performance degradation was observed with increasing learning rates, MCC declined from 0.537 (baseline 1B) to 0.525, 0.476, and 0.445. The lower rate (5×10^{-6}) produced comparable accuracy (75.9%) with a notable sensitivity-specificity trade-off, sensitivity decreased from 79.4% to 74.1% while specificity improved from 72.9% to 77.6%.

4.2.2 Temporal Sampling (Stage 3)

Increasing temporal sampling from 5 to 10, 15, or 20 frames also resulted in progressively worse overall performance despite quadrupling training dataset size. MCC declined from 0.537 (5 frames) to 0.504, 0.476, and 0.477 respectively. As frame count increased from 5 to 15, sensitivity declined from 79.4% to 72.4% while specificity modestly improved from 72.9% to 75.1%, demonstrating substantial temporal redundancy within 50-frame thermal sequences.

4.2.3 Regularisation and Augmentation (Stage 4)

Stage 4 configurations applied additional augmentation strategies on top of baseline augmentation pipeline. Four alternative regularisation strategies were evaluated, AdamW (weight decay $\lambda = 0.01$), MixUp augmentation [39] ($\alpha = 0.2$), Gaussian noise injection ($\sigma = 3.0$ on sensor value), and combined MixUp+Gaussian noise. All strategies produced lower MCC

Figure 2: Comparison of Grad-CAM visualisations between baseline model (1B, top row) and Gaussian noise model (4C, bottom row) on the same subject. Baseline shows class-specific periorbital attention patterns. Gaussian noise model exhibits catastrophic feature collapse with uniform edge/corner attention regardless of class, explaining the dramatic sensitivity reduction.

than baseline (0.469–0.478 vs. 0.537). The most striking finding emerged from Gaussian noise (4C) which induced a dramatic sensitivity-specificity inversion, specificity rose to 82.9% (highest across all configurations of stage 1–5) while sensitivity plummeted to 62.9%. Grad-CAM analysis revealed this was caused by catastrophic feature collapse, the model’s attention shifted entirely to image edges and corners for intoxicated samples, abandoning the physiologically relevant thermal gradients (Fig. 2).

4.2.4 Backbone Architecture (Stage 5)

Despite substantial architectural differences and parameter counts ranging from 3.5M (MobileNet-V2) to 11.7M (ResNet-18), all architectures achieved comparable overall MCC scores (0.475–0.537) with distinct performance profiles. EfficientNet-B0 achieved the highest ROC-AUC (0.892) across all configurations, indicating superior probability ranking. DenseNet-121 achieved the highest sensitivity (82.4%) but lowest specificity (64.7%). MobileNet-V2 produced the best single-modality calibration (ECE = 0.244).

Grad-CAM comparisons revealed architecture-specific attention strategies (Fig. 3): ResNet-18 employed binary presence/absence activation; EfficientNet-B0 exhibited graduated intensity encoding; MobileNet-V2 showed conservative, compact activation; and DenseNet-121 demonstrated expansive activation patterns, mechanistically explaining their respective sensitivity-specificity profiles.

4.3 The Non-Responder Phenomenon

Across all these experiments of stage 1 to 5, we consistently observed the systematic subject-level performance variation persisting regardless of the hyperparameter or architectural configurations (Fig. 4). This pattern was foreshadowed in Stage 1 where a subset of these subjects exhibited consistent misclassification across all four anatomically distinct modalities which suggests that the classification difficulty is rooted in individual physiology rather than region-specific thermal properties. Analysis identified three distinct subject categories based on mean

Table 4: Comprehensive performance comparison across Stages 2-5 (periorbital/eye modality). All metrics shown are mean across 34 LOSO-CV folds. Bold indicates best performance per metric.

Stage	ID	Configuration	MCC	Acc	Sens	Spec	AUC	EER↓	ECE↓
Base	1B	LR=1e-5, 5f, Adam	0.537	76.2	79.4	72.9	0.869	0.118	0.260
S2	2A	LR = 5×10^{-6}	0.525	75.9	74.1	77.6	0.847	0.162	0.265
	2B	LR = 2×10^{-5}	0.476	73.5	77.1	70.0	0.862	0.156	0.275
	2C	LR = 5×10^{-5}	0.445	71.5	72.9	70.0	0.855	0.144	0.279
S3	3A	10 frames	0.504	74.3	77.4	71.2	0.867	0.131	0.254
	3B	15 frames	0.476	73.7	72.4	75.1	0.844	0.158	0.258
	3C	20 frames	0.477	72.9	72.9	72.8	0.846	0.160	0.264
S4	4A	AdamW ($\lambda=0.01$)	0.469	73.2	73.5	72.9	0.868	0.132	0.266
	4B	MixUp ($\alpha=0.2$)	0.470	73.5	78.8	68.2	0.804	0.191	0.301
	4C	Gauss. noise ($\sigma=3$)	0.474	72.9	62.9	82.9	0.804	0.224	0.272
	4D	MixUp + Gaussian	0.478	73.5	75.9	71.2	0.817	0.191	0.291
S5	5A	EfficientNet-B0	0.483	73.5	77.6	69.4	0.892	0.144	0.261
	5B	MobileNet-V2	0.475	72.9	77.6	68.2	0.833	0.176	0.244
	5C	DenseNet-121	0.488	73.5	82.4	64.7	0.857	0.144	0.258

Figure 3: Architecture-specific Grad-CAM visualisations on a representative subject (Stage 5). (a) ResNet-18: binary activation strategy, (b) EfficientNet-B0: graduated intensity encoding, (c) MobileNet-V2: conservative, compact activation, (d) DenseNet-121: expansive activation pattern. Each architecture’s feature learning strategy mechanistically explain its characteristic sensitivity-specificity profile.

classification accuracy across all 14 eye-modality configurations (baseline 1B and stage 2 to 5), approximately 65% of subjects ($n = 22$) achieved consistent performance above chance ($\geq 60\%$ mean accuracy), approximately 29% ($n = 10$) exhibited marginal performance (50–60%) hovering near chance level, and 6% ($n = 2$) showed consistently poor performance ($< 50\%$) including one subject (Subject 32) performing worse than random chance across all these configurations. Whether this pattern generalises beyond the present dataset requires validation with independent cohorts. With $N = 34$, these pro-

Figure 4: Subject-wise accuracy heatmap across all 14 periorbital configurations (baseline 1B and Stages 2– 5). Subjects are sorted by mean performance (left = best, right = worst). Green cell indicates high accuracy, yellow-moderate, red-poor. Approximately 30% subjects remain challenging regardless of model configuration, demonstrating the Non-Responder Phenomenon.

portions should be considered preliminary estimates.

Examination of these challenging subjects revealed no clear demographic pattern. Poor performers spanned the entire age range (18–62 years) and both genders. The phenomenon of non-responder appears idiosyncratic, potentially attributable to genetic polymorphisms in ADH/ALDH enzymes [35], individual thermo-regulatory variation or uncontrolled confounders.

4.4 Stage 6: Score-Level Fusion

Table 5 presents results of Stage 6. The minimum-rule fusion (6B) achieved the highest MCC (0.565) and accuracy (77.9%) among all 20 experimental configurations from stage 1 to 6, with specificity improving substantially from 72.9% to 85.3% while sensitivity decreased from 79.4% to 70.6%. The most prominent benefit was substantially improved probability calibration, with 6B achieving ECE of 0.156, which is the best calibration observed across the entire study, representing a 40%

Table 5: Stage 6 score-level fusion performance comparison. Subject-level evaluation ($n = 34$ subjects \times 2 conditions = 68 classification decisions). Bold indicates best value per metric across all four configurations.

Config.	MCC	Acc	Sens	Spec	AUC	ECE \downarrow
1B (frames)	.537	76.2	79.4	72.9	.869	.260
6A (eye agg.)	.530	76.5	79.4	73.5	.803	.202
6B (min)	.565	77.9	70.6	85.3	.819	.156
6C (max)	.404	69.1	85.3	52.9	.791	.241

improvement over the single modality baseline (1B). Notably, Stages 1-5 metrics were computed at the frame level (5 sober + 5 intoxicated frames per fold) whereas Stage 6 operates at the subject level (1 sober + 1 intoxicated decision per fold). However, intra-modal aggregation alone (6A) produced an MCC of 0.530, only marginally below the frame-level baseline (1B: 0.537), and substantially below the minimum-rule fusion result (6B: 0.565). This confirms that the primary driver of improvement in 6B is inter-modal fusion rather than the aggregation step itself, which produced negligible change from the baseline. Conversely, the maximum-rule fusion (6C) exhibited the opposite trade-off profile, sensitivity increased to 85.3% which is highest across all configurations, while specificity declined to 52.9% (MCC = 0.404, ECE = 0.241). The min and max rules represent complementary deployment strategies, the min-rule favours precision and calibration, while the max rule favours recall for screening where the cost of missing an intoxicated individual far exceeds false alarm costs.

5 Discussion

5.1 Comparison with Prior Work

Table 6 places the present results alongside prior work. The 76.2% accuracy and MCC of 0.537 achieved under LOSO-CV are lower than the 86–98% reported in studies employing subject-dependent or limited subject-independent evaluation [7, 10–12, 36]. This disparity is consistent with the 20–30 percentage point performance drops documented when transitioning from subject-dependent to subject-independent protocols in physiological classification tasks [13, 37], and underscores that prior estimates may not reflect realistic deployment performance on novel individuals.

The only prior subject-independent evaluation with deep learning [12] reported 95.8% accuracy on 10 subjects from a private dataset. While this figure is substantially higher than the present result, several factors complicate direct comparison: the sample size of 10 subjects provides limited statistical power, the dataset was not publicly available for independent verification, and the small cohort may not adequately represent inter-individual variability. The present study, conducted on a public dataset with 34 subjects and full LOSO-CV (34 folds), provides a more conservative but arguably more generalisable benchmark.

Table 6: Comparison with prior thermal intoxication detection studies. SD: subject-dependent; SI: subject-independent.

Study	N	Region	Protocol	Acc (%)	MCC
Koukiou [36]	20	Face	SD	86	—
Koukiou [7]	41	Face	SD	~88	—
Koukiou [9]	41	Eye	SD	~88	—
Neagoe [10]	41	Face	SD	93	—
Neagoe [12]	10	Face	SI	95.8	—
Soltuz [11]	41	Face	SD	93–98	—
Koukiou [46]	41	Face	SD	>86	—
Chai [45]	20	Face	SD	90	—
Ours (eye)	34	Eye	SI (LOSO)	76.2	0.537
Ours (fusion)	34	Eye+Face	SI (LOSO)	77.9	0.565

The present also work introduces evaluation dimensions absent from prior studies. The MCC of 0.537, which accounts for all four quadrants of the confusion matrix, indicates moderate positive correlation between predictions and true labels, substantially above chance but below levels required for standalone deployment. Probability calibration (ECE = 0.156 with fusion), algorithmic fairness analysis through subject-level failure characterisation, and Grad-CAM-based physiological validation are reported here for the first time in this domain.

5.2 Physiological Interpretation of Modality Differences

The superior performance of the periorbital region has a clear physiological basis. This area receives blood supply from branches of the ophthalmic artery, including the supraorbital and supratrochlear arteries, which anastomose extensively with external carotid branches [34]. The rich vascular network combined with thin overlying skin and minimal subcutaneous fat creates favourable conditions for thermal detection of alcohol-induced vasodilation. The inner canthus region, where Grad-CAM analysis revealed concentrated attention for intoxicated classifications, contains dense superficial vasculature that responds rapidly to autonomic changes.

Alcohol-induced peripheral vasodilation occurs through multiple mechanisms, including direct smooth muscle relaxation, nitric oxide release, and prostaglandin synthesis [6, 35]. The facial modality’s lower performance (MCC = 0.407), despite containing periorbital information, is attributable to signal dilution across a larger anatomical area with heterogeneous thermal properties. The palmar modality’s inconsistent performance (MCC = 0.391, highest SD = 0.623) reflects the hand’s active thermoregulatory function [34], while the auricular region’s lowest performance (MCC = 0.347) may be attributable to environmental susceptibility and potential hair occlusion, though further investigation is needed.

These four anatomical locations have not been comprehensively compared under the same experimental settings in any previous investigation. Practical recommendations for sen-

Figure 5: Stage 6 score-level fusion results. (a) Confusion matrices for Eye-only aggregation (6A), Eye+Face minimum-rule fusion (6B), and Eye+Face maximum-rule fusion (6C). (b) ROC curves comparing all fusion configurations. (c) Calibration reliability diagrams showing minimum-rule fusion (6B) achieves best calibration (ECE = 0.156).

rior placement in deployment scenarios are provided by the evidence-based selection of the periorbital area as the most discriminative site.

5.3 Augmentation-Induced Feature Collapse in Thermal Imaging

The finding that Gaussian noise augmentation leads to catastrophic feature collapse, confirmed using Grad-CAM analysis, has significant implications for the design of augmentation strategies in physiological imaging. Unlike natural image classification where noise augmentation often improves robustness [38, 39], thermal intoxication detection relies on subtle thermal gradients that are precisely those most susceptible to pixel-level perturbation. The Gaussian-augmented model discarded periorbital and nasal thermal patterns in favor of high-contrast edge features that maintain stability under noise, thereby impairing its capacity to differentiate intoxication states.

This result implies that in thermal biometric applications

where discriminative features appear as minor intensity gradients rather than structural patterns, typical augmentation techniques can be detrimental. Domain-specific augmentation strategies that preserve thermal gradient information warrant further investigation.

5.4 The Non-Responder Phenomenon and Algorithmic Fairness

The presence of roughly 30% non-responder subjects in all configurations indicates a physiological limitation rather than a computational one. No combination of hyperparameter adjustment, architectural variation, or augmentation technique could save systemically challenging subjects. This result has two implications.

First, in terms of algorithmic fairness, a system with 76% overall accuracy may perform well for the majority of persons while hovering near chance level for a significant minority. For safety-critical applications where false negatives pose a disproportionate danger, aggregate measurements alone may not be

adequate guidance. The EU AI Act [16] explicitly addresses such considerations for high-risk AI systems, requiring representative training data and non-discriminatory performance. Second, this phenomenon parallels findings across biometric domains [40], suggesting that performance improvements will require expanded training populations, subject-specific adaptation approaches, or multimodal sensing with orthogonal physiological signals, rather than continued model optimisation.

5.5 Multimodal Fusion and Calibration

The two inter-modal fusion rules demonstrate a sensitivity-specificity trade-off determined by operator selection. The minimum probability rule (6B) improved overall MCC (0.565) and significantly boosted probability calibration (ECE = 0.156), meeting EASA’s AI Assurance standards for accurately transmitting inference certainty [15]. This conservative method decreased sensitivity from 79.4% to 70.6%, making it acceptable for contexts that require calibrated probability estimations and minimal false-positive rates. The investigation found that the maximum probability rule (6C) had the highest sensitivity (85.3%) but had lower specificity (52.9%) and impaired calibration (ECE = 0.241). This permissive strategy may be appropriate for safety-critical screening scenarios in which the asymmetric cost structure penalizes missed detections, such as pre-flight crew screening, where a false negative poses a safety risk while a false positive only results in a confirmatory breathalyzer test. These two criteria, when combined, enable practitioners to alter the operating point for various deployment cost structures without having to retrain.

5.6 Practical Deployment Implications

While the achieved performance falls short of standalone deployment criteria, the practical context exposes value when viewed in light of existing operating restrictions. According to Indian aviation regulations [4, 5], only 25% of non-flight-crew members are randomly sampled, leaving about 75% untested everyday owing to limited resources. Thermal imaging can be used as a passive, high-throughput pre-screening method for this untested population. This technology is not intended for operational spot checks on the runway or in maintenance hangars, where environmental factors would significantly reduce thermal accuracy. Instead, it is designed for integration into controlled, indoor staff check-in or biometric attendance phases as a gatekeeping pre-screen, flagging individuals for confirmatory testing before they proceed to operational areas. In this hybrid architecture, positive thermal screens trigger confirmatory breathalyser testing, positioning thermal screening as an EASA Level 1 AI system (human assistance) [15], where AI suggests results but human operators make final determinations, satisfying oversight requirements of both EASA and the EU AI Act. Table 7 summarises alignment between the present methodology and emerging aviation AI regulatory requirements.

The technique uses binary categorization (‘Pass’ or ‘Fail’)

Table 7: Alignment of the methodology with emerging AI regulatory frameworks for aviation.

Methodological contribution	Regulatory requirement	Framework
LOSO-CV evaluation	Learning Assurance (Generalisation)	EASA Concept Paper [15]
Grad-CAM analysis	AI Explainability	EASA [15], EU AI Act Art. 13 [16]
Subject-level failure analysis	Fairness, non-discrimination	EU AI Act Art. 10 [16]
Probability calibration (ECE)	Trustworthiness	EASA AI Roadmap [41]
Hybrid deployment proposal	Human oversight, Level 1 AI	EASA [15], FAA Roadmap
Complete documentation	Technical documentation	EU AI Act Art. 11 [16]

rather than attempting to estimate particular blood alcohol concentration (BAC) levels. Estimating accurate BAC exclusively from thermal images is medically unreliable and unlikely to achieve regulatory accuracy thresholds [4, 5], especially considering the Non-Responder Phenomenon. Because this method is intended solely as a pre-screening tool, any alerted individual must undergo a legally valid breathalyzer test, this binary approach is both feasible and legally compatible.

5.7 Limitations

There are certain limitations that should be acknowledged. First, the 34-subject sample size reduces statistical power, as indicated by non-significant Friedman tests despite significant effect sizes. Second, while the proposed deployment strategy focuses on controlled indoor biometric checkpoints, the foundational laboratory dataset does not fully capture real-world variables like unconstrained subject motion, partial facial occlusion, and long-term camera calibration drift; however, modern uncooled LWIR cameras with improved non-uniformity correction can alleviate some of these concerns.

Third, there are 25 men and 9 women in the dataset, which is skewed toward men. Nonetheless, this disparity provides an ecologically sound standard for this particular sector since it roughly reflects the demographic distribution of the targeted aviation workforce in maintenance and ground operations. The composition’s predominately European makeup is still a drawback. Across ethnic groups, genetic variations in the ADH/ALDH enzymes significantly impact peripheral vasodilation and alcohol metabolism [35, 42]. For example, fast facial vasodilation occurs even after moderate alcohol consumption due to ALDH2 deficiency, which is frequently linked to the alcohol flush reaction in East Asian cultures. These people would probably be simpler to identify thermally, which could lead to an increase in sensitivity but also an increase in false-

positive rates among those who visibly flush but do not meet standards for cognitive impairment. This polymorphism may change the system’s operating characteristics and the frequency of the Non-Responder Phenomenon if it is implemented under jurisdictions such as India’s DGCA, requiring region-specific dataset calibration.

Fourth, the original experimental design, which provided a uniform alcohol dose (480 mL of 13% ABV wine) independent of subject body mass (51–110 kg), limits this investigation because it employs a secondary dataset. Examining non-responder subjects showed no consistent correlation between body mass and classification difficulty, despite this uncontrolled pharmacokinetic variable being a limitation. This suggests that the Non-Responder Phenomenon is not directly related to dose-dependent BAC variation. Lastly, the existing models are unable to map the entire temporal curve of alcohol-induced thermal changes due to the dataset’s exclusive binary focus (sober versus 80-minute post-consumption), which complies with pass/fail pre-screening standards.

6 Conclusions

In contrast to previous subject-independent work ($N = 10$), this study offers a subject-independent standard for thermal infrared intoxication detection using deep learning, tested on a public dataset with a larger cohort ($N = 34$) [12]. The LOSO-CV procedure provides calibrated expectations for system design by revealing that the realistic deployment performance (76.2% accuracy, $MCC = 0.537$) is significantly lower than previous estimations (86–98%). Based on both empirical performance and physiological interpretation based on the periorbital vascular structure, the periorbital region is found to be the most efficient imaging site. Grad-CAM research shows that typical augmentation techniques can be detrimental to thermal imaging by causing feature collapse, while also validating the model’s concentration on physiologically relevant regions.

The identification of the Non-Responder Phenomenon, in which about 30% of subjects continue to be difficult regardless of model design, is a first but significant step in comprehending the technological constraints necessary for appropriate deployment. Two complementary operating strategies are provided by score-level fusion of periorbital and facial modalities. The maximum probability rule produces the highest sensitivity (85.3%) for situations where missed detections carry disproportionate costs, while the minimum probability rule achieves the best overall discrimination ($MCC = 0.565$) and probability calibration ($ECE = 0.156$). For practical implementation, regulatory coverage gaps are filled while upholding legal evidential standards via a hybrid architecture that uses thermal imaging as a pre-screening layer and confirmatory breathalyser testing for people flagged.

Future research should prioritise independent validation on demographically diverse populations, potential personalisation approaches for non-responder mitigation, domain specific augmentation strategies for thermal imagery, post-hoc calibration

techniques such as temperature scaling [27], and field validation under practical operational conditions.

CRedit Authorship Contribution Statement

Arghya Dev Mondal: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Writing - original draft, Visualization. **Harkeerat Kaur:** Supervision, Writing - review & editing, Resources, Project administration.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Declaration of Generative AI Use

The authors used AI-assisted tools for LaTeX formatting and language editing of the manuscript. All research design, experimental execution, data analysis, interpretation, and scientific content are entirely the work of the authors.

Ethics Statement

This study is a secondary analysis of a publicly available, anonymised dataset (University of Patras Sober-Drunk Dataset). The original data collection was conducted under ethical oversight at the University of Patras, Greece, as described in the foundational publications [7, 9]. The present secondary analysis involved no human participants, no collection of personal data, and no intervention of any kind; accordingly, no separate ethical approval was required for this study.

Data Availability

The University of Patras Sober-Drunk thermal dataset is publicly available from the dataset creators upon request (<https://old.physics.upatras.gr/sober/>) with the requirement that users cite the foundational publications [7, 9].

Acknowledgements

The authors thank Georgia Koukiou, Ph.D., of the University of Patras, Greece, for generously providing the dataset used in this research. The computational resources provided by the Indian Institute of Technology Jammu are gratefully acknowledged.

References

- [1] International Civil Aviation Organisation, *Annex 1 to the Convention on International Civil Aviation: Personnel Licensing*, 14th ed., ICAO, Montreal, Canada, 2022.
- [2] Federal Aviation Administration, 14 CFR § 91.17 - Alcohol or drugs, Washington, DC, USA, 2006.
- [3] Commission Regulation (EU) 2018/1042 of 23 July 2018 amending Regulation (EU) No 965/2012, 2018.
- [4] Directorate General of Civil Aviation, *Civil Aviation Requirements Section 5, Series F, Part III: Procedure for medical examination of aircraft personnel for alcohol consumption*, DGCA, New Delhi, India, 2019.
- [5] Directorate General of Civil Aviation, *Civil Aviation Requirements Section 5, Series F, Part IV: Procedure for examination of aviation personnel for consumption of psychoactive substances*, DGCA, New Delhi, India, 2019.
- [6] S.C. Malpas, B.J. Robinson, T.J. Maling, Mechanism of ethanol-induced vasodilation, *J. Appl. Physiol.* 68 (1990) 731–734.
- [7] G. Koukiou, V. Anastassopoulos, Neural networks for identifying drunk persons using thermal infrared imagery, *Forensic Sci. Int.* 252 (2015) 69–76.
- [8] G. Gaussorgues, S. Chomet, *Infrared Thermography*, Springer, Dordrecht, 1994.
- [9] G. Koukiou, V. Anastassopoulos, Drunk person screening using eye thermal signatures, *J. Forensic Sci.* 61 (2016) 259–264.
- [10] V.-E. Neagoe, S.-V. Carata, Drunkenness diagnosis using a neural network-based approach for analysis of facial images in the thermal infrared spectrum, in: *E-Health Bioeng. Conf. (EHB)*, 2017, pp. 165–168.
- [11] A.-I. Soltuz, V.-E. Neagoe, Facial thermal image analysis with deep convolutional neural network architectures for subject dependent drunkenness diagnosis, in: *ECAI*, 2021, pp. 1–4.
- [12] V.-E. Neagoe, P. Diaconescu, O. Catrina, An ensemble of deep convolutional neural networks for drunkenness detection using thermal infrared facial imagery, in: *13th Int. Conf. Commun. (COMM)*, Bucharest, Romania, 2020, pp. 147–150.
- [13] S. Kunjan et al., The necessity of leave one subject out (LOSO) cross validation for EEG disease diagnosis, in: *Brain Informatics*, Springer, 2021, pp. 558–567.
- [14] A.J. Mansfield, J.L. Wayman, Best practices in testing and reporting performance of biometric devices, National Physical Laboratory, Teddington, UK, 2002.
- [15] European Union Aviation Safety Agency, *EASA Concept Paper: Guidance for Level 1 & 2 Machine Learning Applications*, EASA, Cologne, Germany, 2024.
- [16] Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act), *Official Journal of the European Union*, 2024.
- [17] A.W. Jones, M.M. Houck, Alcohol pharmacokinetics, in: *Encyclopedia of Forensic Sciences*, 3rd ed., Elsevier, Amsterdam, 2023, pp. 530–541.
- [18] K. He, X. Zhang, S. Ren, J. Sun, Deep residual learning for image recognition, in: *CVPR*, 2016, pp. 770–778.
- [19] J. Deng et al., ImageNet: A large-scale hierarchical image database, in: *CVPR*, 2009, pp. 248–255.
- [20] M. Tan, Q.V. Le, EfficientNet: Rethinking model scaling for convolutional neural networks, in: *ICML*, 2019, pp. 6105–6114.
- [21] A.G. Howard et al., MobileNets: Efficient convolutional neural networks for mobile vision applications, *arXiv:1704.04861*, 2017.
- [22] G. Huang, Z. Liu, L. Van Der Maaten, K.Q. Weinberger, Densely connected convolutional networks, in: *CVPR*, 2017, pp. 2261–2269.
- [23] D.P. Kingma, J. Ba, Adam: A method for stochastic optimization, in: *ICLR*, San Diego, CA, 2015.
- [24] J. Kittler, M. Hatef, R.P.W. Duin, J. Matas, On combining classifiers, *IEEE Trans. PAMI* 20 (1998) 226–239.
- [25] B.W. Matthews, Comparison of the predicted and observed secondary structure of T4 phage lysozyme, *Biochim. Biophys. Acta* 405 (1975) 442–451.
- [26] D. Chicco, G. Jurman, The advantages of the Matthews correlation coefficient (MCC) over F1 score and accuracy in binary classification evaluation, *BMC Genomics* 21 (2020) 6.
- [27] C. Guo, G. Pleiss, Y. Sun, K.Q. Weinberger, On calibration of modern neural networks, in: *ICML*, Sydney, Australia, 2017, pp. 1321–1330.
- [28] J. Demšar, Statistical comparisons of classifiers over multiple data sets, *J. Mach. Learn. Res.* 7 (2006) 1–30.
- [29] M. Friedman, The use of ranks to avoid the assumption of normality implicit in the analysis of variance, *J. Am. Stat. Assoc.* 32 (1937) 675–701.
- [30] F. Wilcoxon, Individual comparisons by ranking methods, *Biometrics Bull.* 1 (1945) 80–83.
- [31] S. Holm, A simple sequentially rejective multiple test procedure, *Scand. J. Stat.* 6 (1979) 65–70.
- [32] J. Cohen, *Statistical Power Analysis for the Behavioral Sciences*, 2nd ed., Routledge, New York, 2013.
- [33] R.R. Selvaraju et al., Grad-CAM: Visual explanations from deep networks via gradient-based localization, in: *ICCV*, 2017, pp. 618–626.
- [34] J.M. Johnson, D.L. Kellogg, Local thermal control of the human cutaneous circulation, *J. Appl. Physiol.* 109 (2010) 1229–1238.
- [35] A.I. Cederbaum, Alcohol metabolism, *Clin. Liver Dis.* 16 (2012) 667–685.

- [36] G. Koukiou, V. Anastassopoulos, Drunk person identification using thermal infrared images, *Int. J. Electron. Secur. Digit. Forensics* 4 (2012) 229–243.
- [37] F. Lotte, A review of classification algorithms for EEG-based brain-computer interfaces: A 10 year update, *J. Neural Eng.* 15 (2018) 031005.
- [38] C. Shorten, T.M. Khoshgoftaar, A survey on image data augmentation for deep learning, *J. Big Data* 6 (2019) 60.
- [39] H. Zhang, M. Cisse, Y.N. Dauphin, D. Lopez-Paz, mixup: Beyond empirical risk minimization, in: *ICLR*, Vancouver, Canada, 2018.
- [40] J. Buolamwini, T. Gebru, Gender shades: Intersectional accuracy disparities in commercial gender classification, in: *Conf. Fairness Account. Transparency*, PMLR, 2018, pp. 77–91.
- [41] European Union Aviation Safety Agency, *EASA Artificial Intelligence Roadmap 2.0: A Human-Centric Approach to AI in Aviation*, EASA, Cologne, Germany, 2023.
- [42] H.J. Edenberg, J.N. McClintick, Alcohol dehydrogenases, aldehyde dehydrogenases, and alcohol use disorders: A critical review, *Alcohol. Clin. Exp. Res.* 42 (2018) 2281–2297.
- [43] A. Sancén-Plaza, L. Contreras-Medina, A. Barranco-Gutiérrez, C. Villaseñor-Mora, J. Martínez, J. Padilla-Medina, Facial recognition for drunk people using thermal imaging, *Math. Probl. Eng.* 2020 (2020) 1–9.
- [44] M.K. Bhuyan, S. Dhawle, P. Sasmal, G. Koukiou, Intoxicated person identification using thermal infrared images and gait, in: *Proc. Int. Conf. Wireless Commun., Signal Process. Netw. (WiSPNET)*, Chennai, India, 2018, pp. 1–3.
- [45] C.-H. Chai, S.F. Abdul Razak, S. Yogarayan, R. Shanmugam, Drunk driver detection using thermal facial images, *Information* 16 (5) (2025) Art. no. 413.
- [46] G. Koukiou, Thermal biometric features for drunk person identification using multi-frame imagery, *Electronics* 11 (23) (2022) 3924.
- [47] G. Hermosilla, J.L. Verdugo, G. Farías, E. Vera, F. Pizarro, M. Machuca, Face recognition and drunk classification using infrared face images, *J. Sens.* 2018 (2018) 1–8.